

Recommended citation: Gigla, B., & Weinig, J. (2019). New framework for civil engineering programs in Germany. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 452-461). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656441.

New Framework for Civil Engineering Programs in Germany

B. Gigla

Technische Hochschule Lübeck

J. Weinig

Fachhochschule Bielefeld, Campus Minden

German Association of Departments of Civil Engineering and Environmental Engineering at Universities of Applied Sciences (GADCEE)

Conference Key Areas: democratic involvement in educational processes, employability as a target of engineering education

Keywords: professional civil engineering, educational standards, accreditation, reference framework, design of bachelor degree courses in civil engineering

ABSTRACT

A common European labour market requires a transparent presentation of professional standards. This is particularly important for civil engineers for three reasons: Civil engineers create products with long life cycles, important resources are bound and buildings have an impact on people, environment and society.

Who defines the prerequisites for the exercise of a profession in civil engineering - universities, state, and chambers of engineers? Due to the diversity of the courses of study, the Chambers of Engineers ultimately want to assess the professional qualification. In the case of academic training, however, teaching and research are granted free. The design of the curricula is the sole responsibility of the universities.

Therefore, to describe employability in civil engineering, a reference framework for bachelor degree courses was developed by an association of stakeholders that incorporates universities, universities of applied sciences, the construction industry, trade unions, chambers of engineers and students.

The reference framework defines learning objectives and competences. It is subdivided into the subject areas "Fundamentals of Engineering", "Planning", "Construction Design" and "Construction Management" with 135 credit points (ECTS). This ensures the necessary breadth and depth of academic education in civil engineering (Bachelor) as a basis for professional qualification. The reference framework is a compromise. The application is optional for the universities, but recommended. It ensures that the definition of professional qualifications in civil engineering programs may remain in the responsibility of the universities. In Germany, civil engineering is the first engineering discipline to succeed in such a reference framework.

1 INTRODUCTION

The entitlement to use the professional title of a civil engineer is regulated differently at international level. In North America, for example, study courses for civil engineers are accredited by professional associations such as ASCE (American Society of Civil Engineers) or Engineers Canada [1]. The intention is to guarantee the requirements for professional engineering registration in the understanding of the association.

In Europe, the European Network for the Accreditation of Engineering Education (ENAE) has established an international, specialist accreditation network. This has not yet played a role in Germany. The European Council of Engineers Chambers surveyed the state of training of civil engineers in the countries of the European Union. Annex VI of the report suggests steps to develop "Common Training Principles for Engineers" (CTP) [2].

In Germany, the title "Civil Engineer" has been associated with the university degree "Diplom-Ingenieur" (Dipl.-Ing.) for about 150 years. Law in Germany has regulated the title since 1970. The underlying engineering laws are within the authority of 16 federal states. To avoid difficulties in mutual recognition, the engineering laws follow a coordinated "Template Engineer Act", which is drafted by the Conference of Ministers of the Federal States responsible for Economic Affairs. Previously, the study of a technical or scientific discipline with a "Diplom" (university degree Dipl.-Ing.) and a standard period of study of at least three years at a state or state-recognized academic institution were sufficient to earn the professional title "engineer". All the experts involved have so far accepted this pragmatic legal regulation as good and sufficient.

As a result of the Bologna Process and the European Professional Recognition Directive an adaptation of the engineering laws was necessary (compare: Directive 2005/36/EC amended by Directive 2013/55/EU). The replacement of Dipl.-Ing. degrees by Bachelor and Master degrees because of the Bologna reform has led to uncertainty in professional practice. Human resources departments criticized the fact that some names of degree programmes do not allow clear conclusions about the acquired competences. In reaction it was discussed to regulate required study contents by law. For this purpose, the formulation that the course of studies must be predominantly characterized by the fields of mathematics, computer science, natural sciences and technology was preferred for simplification purposes. In some federal states, the statutory chambers of engineers have also attempted to exert influence. The Chambers of Engineers proposed to combine the right to use the professional title of engineer with a membership in the chamber.

The Universities see both, legal regulations governing study content and mandatory chamber memberships for their graduates as illegitimate interference with their constitutionally guaranteed freedom of research and teaching. An association of stakeholders therefore developed the introduced reference framework for civil engineering [3]. To describe prerequisites for employability, recommendations were developed for teaching volume and obtained competences. A study programme matrix was developed to review these recommendations, enabling each university to check the course content and to make clear to what extent it deviates from the

reference framework. This approach is aimed to make the description of employability more transparent in accreditation procedures.

2 STUDY SYSTEM IN GERMANY

2.1 Historical Development

From the middle of the 19th century to the 1960s, civil engineers in Germany were qualified at regional polytechnic academies. These gradually acquired the status of technical universities or universities of applied sciences. Due to a shortage of engineers in the 1960s, additional engineering institutions were founded in the federal states. At the beginning of the 1970s, these engineering schools were integrated into the newly founded “universities of applied sciences” nationwide.

The universities of applied sciences provide a focus of qualification oriented at the classical German dual education: Theoretical knowledge is applied in practice and practical knowledge is questioned by theory. The academic staff at universities of applied Sciences need to have a PhD degree in civil engineering and is supposed to possess professional experience in leading position outside of the university.

2.2 From Diplom-Ingenieur to Bachelor of Engineering

The degrees at the universities on the one hand and at the universities of applied sciences on the other hand were titled slightly different, either Dipl.-Ing. (Univ.) or Dipl.-Ing. (FH). The graduates of the universities of applied sciences were very well received on the labour market, especially in all tasks of planning, work preparation, construction execution and site management. Their appreciation in the construction industry in terms of salary was not inferior to that of university engineers.

In the course of the Bologna Process in the European education area, the concept of knowledge transfer changed to describe learning outcome. Today, learning outcome is specified and extended with the concept of the mediation of competences [4]. A further objective of the Bologna Process was the differentiation of the courses offered. The aim was to respond more flexibly to the graduate needs of industry. The inclinations and talents of the students should be developed better and more precisely in these differentiated study programmes.

Today's understanding of education in Europe is based on diversity, but equivalence on academic (tertiary) education. Tertiary education no longer distinguishes between types of higher education institutions. It differentiates only in education levels. Consecutive, building on one another, i.e. in Bachelor's, Master's and doctorate degrees. Additions "Univ." and "FH" at the degree Dipl.-Ing. are therefore obsolete.

2.3 Civil engineer's responsibility in society

The "classical" civil engineers, or rather: those who perform the classical construction task, have a special responsibility for their actions. With construction measures, capital is tied up for the long term, the built environment is shaped and the energy and resource requirements are decisively determined. The state has delegated this task and responsibility to the Chambers of Engineers on a self-organising basis. In Germany, civil engineers are often self-employed and perform important public tasks.

There are 16 state chambers of engineers in Germany. The “Bundesingenieurkammer” (Federal Chamber of Engineers) is the umbrella organisation. These chambers are so-called “public corporations”, i.e. they have an independent role between state and engineer, a self-organized part of society.

The professors, with the constitutional right to freedom in research and teaching, are also a special species in the German understanding of the state. The professors are civil servants for life (the German variant of the tenure track) with special duties towards state and society. Thus it is the duty and right of professors to contribute to the development of their subject area/course of study.

Collisions between the two groups resulted from this competing task of the state, on the one hand to the Chamber of Engineers and on the other hand to the professors to continue the development of civil engineering education. One solution is the introduced reference framework to describe the employability of graduates of bachelor degree courses in civil engineering.

But other regions of the world are also working on uniform standards of civil engineering education with regard to teaching content, the social responsibility of engineers and uniform ethical principles, such as in East Africa [5].

Engineers Canada has already formulated such standards [1]:

- Professionalism: An understanding of the roles and responsibilities of the professional engineer in society, especially the primary role of protection of the public and the public interest;
- Impact of engineering on society and the environment: (...). Such ability includes an understanding of the interactions that engineering has with the economic, health, safety, legal, and cultural aspects of society (...)
- Ethics and equity: An ability to apply professional ethics, accountability, and equity.

2.4 Bachelor degree: Is there a difference between the University and the University of Applied Sciences?

The university degrees are the same in the individual (federal) states, and between universities and the university of applied sciences they are of equal value, but different in orientation. The universities of applied sciences attach particular importance to the (immediate) professional qualification of the graduates. This is achieved by the academic and practical qualification of the professors.

Research in the construction industry in Germany is low compared to other sectors (e.g. health, pharmacy, automotive) according to the classical key figures (research expenditure according to turnover). This is also due to the special structure of the construction industry in Germany. There are 760.000 employees in the main construction sector and more than 70.000 companies plus so-called self-employed individuals. This means an average of 10 employees per company. What is special about this is that these (craft) enterprises do not make any strategic considerations due to their small size. To a certain extent, craft enterprises work "on demand" by definition and not according to a marketing concept.

Innovations in the construction industry are often brought in as a result of practical research. Immediate solution concepts for a practical construction task. This is the typical business of professors before their teaching activities.

3 REFERENCE FRAMEWORK TO DESCRIBE THE EMPLOYABILITY IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

3.1 Basic Principles

The design of study programs must remain in the sole responsibility of the universities to respect the granted freedom of research and teaching. In Germany, the selected qualification goals are reviewed within the framework of accreditation procedures according to the rules of the Stiftung Akkreditierungsrat (Accreditation Council Foundation). The German accreditation system is closely related to the objectives of the study structure reform and the Bologna Process in connection with the meanwhile established European and international standards of quality assurance. These include:

- The quality responsibility of the universities;
- uniform standards with regard to qualification goals, studyability and the quality of the processes;
- freedom of research and teaching as well as the free choice of educational institution guaranteed by fundamental law;
- diversity, comparability and transparency;
- expert-centred accreditation procedure;
- stakeholder participation;
- orientation towards qualification goals and competences.

In addition to the technical aspects, the qualification goals also include scientific qualification and the ability to take up qualified employment [6].

To evaluate the employability ("Beruflichkeit") of the graduates of a study programme in the accreditation procedure, an outcome-oriented reference framework for bachelor degree course in civil engineering is required. It was developed in a voluntary association of stakeholders [3]. The participants included universities, universities of applied sciences, the construction industry, the building trade, the "Oberprüfungsamt für den höheren Technischen Verwaltungsdienst" (governmental examination board), students, chambers of engineers and other stakeholder. One reason for the project was the concern that accreditation procedures might create a predominance of individual scientific opinions in the validation of the employability.

The reference framework describes fields of competence with a volume of 135 credit points (ECTS) which should be covered within a bachelor degree course in civil engineering to ensure the necessary breadth in academic education. To describe employability, a learning objective-oriented matrix is defined in which the obtained competences in the subject areas "technical basics", "engineering design and planning", "structural design" and "engineering economics and management" can be compared with objectives across all courses. The frame of reference refers only to bachelor degree courses in civil engineering, the application is voluntary.

A very large circle of stakeholders was represented (e.g. 85.000 companies in different construction sectors), so that the reference framework received broad attention. It is also seen to be helpful that universities and universities of applied sciences have jointly agreed on the description of employability for civil engineering. The stakeholders agreed to ensure that the reference framework will be considered within all accreditation procedures for bachelor degree courses in civil engineering at universities and universities of applied sciences in Germany.

3.2 Concept of the reference framework

A main target of the stakeholders involved was to provide a well-founded and broad knowledge of civil engineering. This profile of an “allrounder” is regarded as a prerequisite for employability and basis for specialisation areas, which can be further developed within the framework of a master programme.

For this reason, the reference framework reflects sectors of competence which the stakeholders consider to be essential and which should be covered within a bachelor degree course in civil engineering. These fields of competence are summarised in *Table 1*, based on [7].

Knowledge, skills and competences are listed in the reference framework to specify the sectors of competence. These are provided as guidelines: Full implementation is not expected in every case. The selection and focus of each course will be left to the specific course design. It is assumed that the sections of competence are covered with 135 credit points (ECTS). Assuming 30 hours of workload per credit point and a total of 30 credits per semester (six month of study), this equates to 4.5 semesters of study, leaving time to set priorities in optional modules or to pursue one's own specialist interests. A total of 180 credit points are awarded for a 6-semester bachelor degree course in civil engineering. At universities of applied sciences seven semesters are standard with 210 credit points.

Table 1. Sectors of competence which should be covered within a bachelor degree course in civil engineering [3]

Sectors of competence	Courses in civil engineering, e.g.:
Technical basics	mathematics, computer sciences, digital building construction, building physics, engineering mechanics, structural design, building materials science, surveying, economics, laws, ecology
Structural and engineering design	Structural analysis, concrete and masonry, steel construction, wooden construction, geotechnical engineering
Water engineering	Water resources management, hydraulic engineering, urban water management
Management of resources	Waste management, recycling management
Transportation	Traffic and transport planning, road construction, public traffic systems, urban and regional planning
Construction and engineering management	Management of building projects and processes, business economics, project planning and scheduling

Until today, the construction industry has hardly complained about a lack of employability among graduates. It is regarded as usual to "familiarise" entrants with the job for a certain training period and to introduce them internally to the job requirements. At the beginning of their career, graduates are usually accompanied by a suitably qualified, experienced and responsible person.

For the first time, the introduced reference framework describes the level of competence of graduates required from the point of view of “construction practice”. Construction industry and building trade criticised the fact that so far the competencies of the graduates in the areas of technical basics and structural design have strongly predominated, compare *Fig. 1*.

On the job, a higher proportion of competences in engineering economics and management and engineering design and planning is required. Civil engineers must be able to assess the impact, consequences and economic viability of their decisions. A bachelor degree course in civil engineering has to prepare for this demand and the mandatory basic competences must be imparted. For this reason, the stakeholders are regarding the ratio shown in *Fig. 2* as necessary for the competences obtained within a bachelor degree course to guarantee employability.

"traditional" bachelor degree course:
academic competences[%]

Fig. 1. Sample of the percentage distribution of competences in “traditional” bachelor degree courses in civil engineering

Reference Framework:
academic competences [%]

Fig. 2. Percentage distribution of competences recommended by the reference framework to fulfil requirements of professional civil engineering

In order to give the universities sufficient flexibility in designing their programmes, a new approach to review the distribution of competences has been developed: Basis

are the four segments of competences in Fig. 1 and 2 (technical basics, structural design, engineering design and planning, engineering economics and management). These are referred to as “dimensions of competence”.

The stakeholders agreed not to recommend any concrete stipulations with regard to the distribution of courses. Rather, an overarching recommendation was made that 40% of the entire programme should cover the dimension of competence "technical basics" and 20% each the competence dimensions "structural design", "engineering design and planning" and "engineering economics and management". Large parts of the course will cover all four areas [3].

Since there are complaints in accreditation practice about an overweight of formal testing procedures, the criteria applied and the procedure for checking the distribution of competences should be transparent and easy to handle. For this purpose, a bachelor degree course matrix was developed with which the competence profile of a study programme or of individual study and specialisation fields can be worked out and compared with the competence distribution 40%/20%/20%/20% recommended by the reference framework according to Fig. 2.

What is new here is the approach that the ratio of competences taught is not to be achieved on basis of the courses, but on the average of all compulsory courses, based on 135 credit points. For this purpose, the distribution of competences for each module must be determined and summarised. The procedure is explained in Table 2.

The distribution of competences depends on the individual design of the module. For example, a module such as "Structural Engineering" can contain elements from engineering planning, structural design and construction management. Individual modules may therefore cover all four competence dimensions, each in different proportions. This should at the same time emphasise the complexity of construction tasks and the job reality of engineering activities in the construction industry.

Table 2. Principle of the bachelor degree course matrix: In the compulsory area, the competence shares in the dimensions of competence "technical basics", "engineering design and planning", "structural design" and "engineering economics and management" are recorded in each module and weighted based on 135 credit points in total. The table shows an intermediate status for five example modules. The distribution of competences depends on the individual design of the module. Overall, the distribution of competencies should be 40%/20%/20%/20% as shown in Fig. 2.

Acquired competences→ Modul↓	ECTS	technical basics	engineering design and planning	structural design	engineering economics and management
Building Physics	5	70%	15%	15%	0%
Structural Masonry	5	10%	30%	50%	10%
Hydraulic Engineering	5	20%	40%	30%	10%
Management	5	0%	10%	0%	90%
Other Module	5	x	x	x	x
Subtotal	20	100%	95%	95%	110%
Mean obligatory module	135	3,7%	3,5%	3,5%	4,1%

Recommendation	135	40%	20%	20%	20%
----------------	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

A sample spreadsheet with instructions for use is available for download to simplify processing during accreditation. The "mandatory programme" listed in the frame of reference should correspond to at least 135 credit points. The additional credit points required will be awarded within the framework of the bachelor thesis as well as with the acquisition of additional, possibly interdisciplinary competences.

Further criteria are the equipment of the university and the imparting of "soft skills". The frame of reference proposes a questionnaire for reviewing the equipment. Soft skills must be the subject of higher education, but cannot be assigned to any field of competence in terms of content. For this reason, a selection of competences is defined that should be integrated into the teaching of subject content. In addition, the reference framework recommends an internship of at least 12 weeks during the course of study.

The recommended distribution of competences 40%/20%/20%/20% should not be applied rigidly in a formalistic manner, but provides an orientation framework. However, deviations are made transparent and can be assessed in the accreditation procedure.

4 SUMMARY

The presented reference framework describes the current professional understanding in civil engineering in Germany in a transparent and outcome-oriented way. It was developed by a large circle of stakeholders and contributes to ensuring that the description of employability of graduates in all bachelor degree courses in civil engineering remains the sole responsibility of the universities. In Germany, civil engineering is the first engineering discipline to have succeeded in describing a profession in this way on an academic basis. In addition, universities and universities of applied sciences have agreed on one description of employability despite their different qualification goals.

For the first time, the reference framework takes into account the level of competence of the graduates required from the point of view of construction practice. A higher proportion of competences in engineering economics and management and in engineering design and planning are required for the practice of the profession. Civil engineers must be able to assess the implications, consequences and economic viability of decisions. In bachelor degree courses in civil engineering, the prerequisites must be defined, the mandatory basic competences have to be imparted and a corresponding awareness should be developed. The reference framework provides criteria and gives universities sufficient flexibility in designing their degree programmes without restricting the legally guaranteed freedom of research and teaching.

This paper is intended to contribute to the discussion of professionalism and occupation in accreditation practice also in an international context. The presented

reference framework is a successful example for „democratic involvement in educational processes“.

REFERENCES

- [1] EngineersCanada (2018), Canadian Engineering Accreditation Board: „ 2018 Accreditation Criteria and Procedures“. Engineers Canada, 55 Metcalfe Street, Suite 300, Ottawa, ON K1P 6L5, November 2018
- [2] European Council of Engineers Chambers (ECEC) (2017): “Common Training Principles for Engineers (491/PP/GRO/IMA/15/15123), Final Project Report”. ECEC Secretariat, Karlsgasse 9/2, 1040 Wien, Austria, 25th. of January, 2017
- [3] Akkreditierungsverbund für Studiengänge des Bauwesens (ASBau) e.V. (2019): „Referenzrahmen für Studiengänge des Bauingenieurwesens (Bachelor)“. ASBau, Kurfürstenstraße 129, 10785 Berlin, Germany, 16.1.2019
- [4] Kultusministerkonferenz (2017): „Qualifikationsrahmen für deutsche Hochschulabschlüsse“. Im Zusammenwirken von Hochschulrektorenkonferenz und Kultusministerkonferenz und in Abstimmung mit Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung erarbeitet und am 16.02.2017 beschlossen, Sekretariat der Ständigen Konferenz der Kultusminister der Länder in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland, Taubenstraße 10, 10117 Berlin, Germany
- [5] Weinig, J., Willms, J., Heincke, C. (2011): „EU-Projekt Afrika, Modernizing Construction: Capacitating East African IOs in the Construction Value Chain“, Teilprojekt Licensing Systems and Tool Rental System in Uganda, Kenya und Ethiopia with Ingenieurkammer Bau NRW, 2010 to 2011
- [6] Arbeitsgruppe Fachlichkeit und Beruflichkeit des Akkreditierungsrates (2015): „Fachlichkeit und Beruflichkeit in der Akkreditierung“. Abschlussbericht und Empfehlungen vom 06.02.2015, Stiftung Akkreditierungsrat, Adenauerallee 73, 53113 Bonn, Germany
- [7] Fachbereichstag Bauingenieurwesen (2015): „Kenntnisse, Fertigkeiten und Kompetenzen im Kernstudium von Bachelorstudiengängen des Bauingenieurwesens an Hochschulen für angewandte Wissenschaften“. German Association of Departments of Civil Engineering at Universities of Applied Sciences (GADCE), Professor Dr.-Ing. Horst Werkle, Hochschule Konstanz Technik, Wirtschaft und Gestaltung, Brauneggerstr. 55, April 2015